

ANTIBACTERIAL EFFECT OF ESSENTIAL OILS AGAINST FOODBORNE MICROORGANISM *ESCHERICHIA COLI*, *STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS*, *PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA* AND *CANDIDA ALBICANS*

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The growing risk of antibiotic resistance has driven the scientific interest of alternative methods development suitable for treatment of animals and food products. Essential oils have been proven to be effective against various bacteria, yeasts and molds. The aim of our study was to evaluate the effectiveness of thyme, cinnamon, black pepper and mint essential oils against type strains of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (*P. aeruginosa*) and *Candida albicans* (*C. albicans*). Antimicrobial activity was determined by measuring the inhibition zones on Mueller Hinton agar. The essential oils were tested using a ten-fold decreasing concentration gradient (from 100% to 10%). Results showed limited inhibition zones for *P. aeruginosa* to all tested essential oils. *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *C. albicans* were inhibited significantly, whereas the cinnamon and thyme essential oils were with highest antimicrobial effect. These findings highlight the potential of selected essential oils as natural alternatives for antimicrobial agents.

Key words: antimicrobial effect, essential oils, foodborne pathogens, antibiotic resistance, *in-vitro* testing.

Introduction

The escalating antimicrobial resistance of foodborne pathogens to traditional agents poses a significant challenge to animal and human health and the food industry. Key pathogens include *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *P. aeruginosa* (Raut & Karuppaiyil, 2014; WHO, 2020). Driven by increasing consumer demand for natural and minimally processed foods, there is growing interest in replacing or supplementing conventional antimicrobial agents with plant-derived alternatives (Chauhan & Rao, 2024).

Essential oils extracted from plants offer a safe and environmentally friendly alternative with potent antimicrobial potential. They contain bioactive compounds—phenols, terpenes, and aldehydes—that exert activity by disrupting the cell membrane, increasing permeability, inhibiting enzymes, and interfering with metabolic functions (Burt, 2004; Nazzaro *et al.*, 2013). Studies have shown that the phenolic monoterpenes thymol and carvacrol, the major constituents of thyme essential oil, possess strong antimicrobial and antifungal activity and are effective even against antibiotic-resistant strains (Raut & Karuppaiyil, 2014; Mihaylova *et al.*, 2025).

The proper extraction method, such as steam distillation or supercritical CO₂ extraction, is critical for preserving these bioactive components and the essential oils antimicrobial activity. Research has demonstrated that essential oils from thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*), cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), black pepper (*Piper nigrum*), and peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) are particularly effective against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *C. albicans* (Raut & Karuppaiyil, 2014). Dorman & Deans (2000) found that these oils exhibit an inhibitory effect at low concentrations by disrupting the lipid mem-

brane and ionic balance. Specifically, cinnamon essential oil shows a strong effect on Gram-negative bacteria, with a 4% concentration determined as most effective against *E. coli* (Adams *et al.*, 2019).

Cinnamon essential oil, rich in cinnamaldehyde, has also demonstrated a potent inhibitory effect against a wide spectrum of pathogens, including *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and *C. albicans* (Dorman & Deans, 2000; Atki *et al.*, 2019). Black pepper and peppermint essential oils exhibit more selective antimicrobial activity, with their efficacy varying according to microbial species and concentration (Alves *et al.*, 2023; Mahboubi & Kazempour, 2014).

Recent Bulgarian studies further support the antimicrobial potential of essential oils. Mihaylova *et al.* (2025) demonstrated strong antibacterial effects of thyme and oregano essential oils against *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*, alone and in combination with antibiotics. Tsankova *et al.* (2025) reported enhanced antibacterial activity when *Thymus vulgaris* essential oil was combined with conventional antimicrobial agents. Earlier work by Popova & Bankova (2016) and Parzhanova *et al.* (2023) confirmed the effectiveness of essential oils derived from Bulgarian medicinal plants against clinically significant bacteria and fungi.

The extraction method – including steam distillation, cold pressing or solvent extraction—plays a critical role in preserving the bioactive components responsible for antimicrobial activity. Variations in chemical composition, influenced by plant species, geographical origin, harvesting conditions and extraction technology, can lead to differences in antimicrobial potency (Burt, 2004; Nazzaro *et al.*, 2013).

The present study aims to evaluate the antimicrobial activity of thyme, cinnamon, black pepper and peppermint essential oils against selected foodborne pathogens and to assess their potential application as natural antimicrobial agents in the food industry.

Materials and Methods

Bacterial strains and cultivation

Laboratory analyses were performed with type strains of *E. coli* (ATCC25922), *S. aureus* (ATCC25923), *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC27853) and *C. albicans* (ATCC 10231) purchased from the National Bank for Industrial Microorganisms and Cell Cultures, Sofia, Bulgaria.

Lyophilized strains were initially suspended in sterile Mueller Hinton Broth (MHB, HiMedia Laboratories, Mumbai, India) and incubated for 24 hours at their optimal temperature (37°C for bacteria and 30°C for *C. albicans*). Fresh colonial cultures were obtained by subsequent inoculation onto Mueller Hinton Agar (MHA, HiMedia Laboratories, Mumbai, India). Stock cultures were prepared by freezing in 2 ml Brain-Heart Infusion broth (BHI, Merck KGaA, Germany) supplemented with 15% glycerol (v/v) and stored at -80°C until use.

Essential oils and preparation

Natural essential oils of thyme (*Thymus vulgaris*), black pepper (*Piper nigrum*), cinnamon (*Cinnamomum zeylanicum*), and peppermint (*Mentha piperita*) were used, purchased from dōTERRA (Pleasant Grove, Utah, USA). Prior to testing, each essential oil was diluted (v/v) in liquid coconut oil to prepare a gradient of concentrations: 100% (pure EO), 90%, 80%, 70%, 60%, 50%, 40%, 30%, 20%, and 10%.

Positive and negative controls

For positive control, standard antibiotic discs were used as reference inhibitors: gentamicin (10 µg) for bacteria and nystatin (100 U) for *C. albicans*. For negative control, liquid coconut oil (the dilution vehicle) was applied in sterile wells to confirm the absence of intrinsic antimicrobial activity.

Agar well diffusion method

The antimicrobial activity was determined using the agar well diffusion method.

1. **Preparation of microbial suspension:** After thawing, each strain was cultured on Mueller Hinton Agar. An initial bacterial suspension was prepared by suspending fresh colonies in sterile saline to achieve a cell concentration of 1.5×10^8 CFU/mL. This concentration was standardized using a McFarland Densitometer (Biosan Sia, Riga, Latvia) at 600 nm.
2. **Inoculation of agar:** Mueller Hinton Agar was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions and after cooling to 40–45°C, the agar was inoculated with the standardized microbial suspension at a ratio of 1 ml per 100 ml of agar medium. The inoculated agar was poured into disposable Petri dishes (90 mm diameter) using the single-layer technique described by Okerman *et al.* (2007).
3. **Application of essential oils and incubation:** After solidification, a single circular well (11 mm diameter) was aseptically created in the center of the agar using a sterile cork borer. A 100 µl aliquot of each gradient essential oil concentration was applied to the well using an automatic micropipette. All samples were prepared in duplicate Petri dishes and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C (bacteria) or 30°C (*C. albicans*).
4. **Measurement:** The diameter of the resulting circular zone of inhibition around the well was measured in triplicate along three diametrical directions, recorded in millimeters. The entire study was performed in duplicate at 14-day intervals.

The interpretation of inhibition zones followed the classification described by Rusenova and Parvanov (2009). According to their criteria, inhibition diameters of 25 mm or greater were considered to indicate a strong antimicrobial effect, while zones ranging between 15 and 24 mm were categorized as a moderate effect. Inhibition zones between 10 and 14 mm were interpreted as a weak effect, and diameters below 10 mm were classified as indicating no antimicrobial activity.

Justification for microorganism selection

The microorganisms used in this study—*E. coli* (ATCC 25922), *S. aureus* (ATCC 25923), *P. aeruginosa* (ATCC 27853), and *C. albicans* (ATCC 10231)—were selected because they represent clinically and foodborne relevant pathogens with well-characterized antimicrobial resistance profiles. These strains are widely used as international reference ATCC strains, ensuring methodological standardization and enabling comparison with previously published studies on essential oils.

Other important foodborne pathogens such as *Salmonella spp.*, *Campylobacter spp.*, and *Listeria monocytogenes* were not included due to methodological limitations, biosafety requirements, and the need for specialized cultivation conditions that exceeded the scope of the present work. Their inclusion is planned for future studies aimed at expanding the applicability of essential oils in food safety.

Field isolates from animals or food products were not tested in this study. ATCC strains were chosen to ensure reproducibility and to minimize biological variability. However, future research will incorporate field isolates to better reflect real-world microbial diversity and resistance patterns.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using GraphPad Prism Software (GraphPad Software Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA). Data processing included the calculation of mean values, standard deviations (SD), and standard error of the mean (SEM). Differences between treatments were analyzed using one-way ANOVA with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Results from antimicrobial activity calculated according to the measured millimeters of the diameter of each inhibition zones using agar well diffusion method are given in tables by tested 4 essential oils. Inhibitor effect is analysed after basic statistical calculations, as in the presented tables mean \pm standard deviation (mm) are given. The higher inhibition zone diameters indicate stronger antimicrobial activity. Statistically significant differences are evaluated at $p < 0.05$, as differences in results between treatments of different oil concentrations against the same microorganism.

As shown in Table 1, thyme oil demonstrated high activity against *E. coli*, with a maximum inhibition zone of 34.67 ± 5.25 mm at 100% concentration. As the concentration decreased, the antimicrobial effect gradually weakened, reaching 11.72 ± 0.40 mm at 20% and 11.00 ± 0.00 mm at 10%. In *S. aureus*, a similar pattern was observed, with the strongest activity at 100% (34.67 ± 5.25 mm) and a progressive reduction in activity at lower concentrations, reaching the threshold of no activity (<10 mm) at 10%. In contrast, for *P. aeruginosa*, only weak activity was detected, with a maximum inhibition zone of 17.30 ± 0.38 mm at 100%. Below 50%, the activity dropped to 11.00 mm, corresponding to minimal or no antimicrobial effect.

Table 1: Inhibition zone (mm) of thyme essential oil for tested microorganisms.

Thyme, %	Strains			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
100	34.67 ± 5.25	$34.67 \pm 5.25^*$	$17.30 \pm 0.38^*$	$49.37 \pm 0.83^*$
90	$35.87 \pm 0.20^*$	$29.38 \pm 0.78^*$	$13.52 \pm 0.52^*$	$43.72 \pm 0.31^*$
80	$33.38 \pm 0.78^*$	$27.67 \pm 0.39^*$	11.00 ± 0.25	$39.62 \pm 0.49^*$
70	$31.38 \pm 0.78^*$	$25.78 \pm 0.39^*$	11.72 ± 0.40	$35.63 \pm 0.39^*$
60	27.93 ± 0.64	$21.67 \pm 0.39^*$	11.38 ± 0.45	33.55 ± 0.45
50	$27.30 \pm 0.63^*$	19.73 ± 0.42	11.00 ± 0.00	$31.73 \pm 0.32^*$
40	$23.60 \pm 0.47^*$	$19.05 \pm 0.78^*$	11.00 ± 0.00	$23.72 \pm 0.37^*$
30	$19.38 \pm 0.53^*$	14.60 ± 0.40	11.00 ± 0.00	11.00 ± 0.00
20	11.72 ± 0.40	12.53 ± 0.49	11.00 ± 0.00	11.00 ± 0.00
10	11.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	11.00 ± 0.00	11.00 ± 0.00
Positive control	22.00 ± 0.00	21.00 ± 0.00	18.00 ± 0.00	20.00 ± 0.00
Negative control	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00	0.00 ± 0.00

* Statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) observed among inhibition zones of tested oil concentrations against the same microorganism.

The strongest antimicrobial activity of thyme essential oil was observed against *C. albicans*, with an inhibition zone of 49.37 ± 0.83 mm at 100% and a still substantial effect at 50% ($31.73 \pm$

0.32 mm). According to the criteria of Rusenova & Parvanov (2009), thyme oil exhibited a strong effect against *C. albicans*, moderate effect against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, and weak effect against *P. aeruginosa*.

According to Table 2, black pepper essential oil showed a maximum inhibition zone of 30.00 ± 1.30 mm against *E. coli* at 100%. The effect gradually decreased with lower concentrations but remained detectable even at 10% (19.38 ± 0.63 mm). In *S. aureus*, a similar pattern was observed, but at concentrations of 20% and 10%, no antimicrobial activity (<10 mm) was detected. For *P. aeruginosa* and *C. albicans*, no inhibition zones were observed at any concentration, indicating an absence of antimicrobial activity. According to the activity criteria, black pepper oil demonstrated a moderate effect against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, but was ineffective against *P. aeruginosa* and *C. albicans*.

Table 2: Inhibition zone (mm) of black paper essential oil for tested microorganisms.

Black paper, %	Strains			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
100	30.00±1.30*	27.52±0.52*	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
90	29.67±0.38	27.52±0.52	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
80	28.13±0.78*	27.63±0.38	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
70	25.42±0.79	27.67±0.37*	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
60	25.37±0.77	25.67±0.42	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
50	25.05±0.67	24.70±0.32	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
40	24.50±0.51	23.55±0.47	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
30	23.68±0.48*	23.77±0.21*	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
20	19.40±0.51	00.00±0.00	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
10	19.38±0.63	00.00±0.00	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
Positive control	22.00±0.00	21.00±0.00	18.00±0.00	20.00±0.00
Negative control	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00

* Statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) observed among inhibition zones of tested oil concentrations against the same microorganism.

Table 3: Inhibition zone (mm) of cinnamon essential oil for tested microorganisms.

Cinnamon, %	Strains			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
100	45.17±0.82*	44.42±0.66*	23.52±0.52*	39.42±4.57*
90	44.97±1.11	44.43±0.56*	23.70±0.39	41.10±0.96*
80	43.05±0.88*	41.00±0.95*	23.32±0.70	35.55±0.77
70	41.27±0.81	39.45±0.75	21.05±0.95	34.50±0.49
60	40.18±0.74	39.33±0.76	23.13±0.95*	35.48±0.53*
50	40.00±0.95*	39.10±0.68*	23.22±0.78	35.48±0.53
40	37.52±0.52	37.60±0.42	21.67±0.98*	34.73±0.42
30	37.53±0.49	37.60±0.42	19.38±0.78	34.37±0.50
20	37.33±0.75*	37.40±0.47*	19.07±0.67*	33.55±0.54
10	28.88±0.98	29.55±0.45	13.18±1.16	31.57±0.49
Positive control	22.00±0.00	21.00±0.00	18.00±0.00	20.00±0.00
Negative control	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00

* Statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) observed among inhibition zones of tested oil concentrations against the same microorganism.

The results for cinnamon essential oil are presented in Table 3. Cinnamon essential oil exhibited the highest antimicrobial activity across all tested pathogens. Against *E. coli*, inhibition reached 45.17 ± 0.82 mm at 100%, and a strong activity persisted even at 10% (28.88 ± 0.98 mm). A similarly strong effect was recorded for *S. aureus*, with inhibition zones of 44.42 ± 0.66 mm (100%) and 29.55 ± 0.45 mm (10%).

In *P. aeruginosa*, cinnamon oil demonstrated stronger activity than all other essential oils, with inhibition of 23.52 ± 0.52 mm at 100%, although the effect decreased at lower concentrations. Against *C. albicans*, cinnamon essential oil exhibited a strong antimicrobial effect, with a zone of 39.42 ± 4.57 mm at 100%, which remained substantial across all concentrations.

Table 4: Inhibition zone (mm) of mint essential oil for tested microorganisms.

Mint, %	Strains			
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
100	25.50±0.40*	24.33±0.41*	11.00±0.00	23.67±0.39*
90	24.13±0.35*	21.38±0.38*	11.00±0.00	18.62±0.31
80	20.43±0.30	19.87±0.33	11.00±0.00	18.60±0.30
70	20.00±0.28	19.77±0.31	11.00±0.00	17.62±0.28
60	19.10±0.25	19.63±0.29	11.00±0.00	17.57±0.27
50	17.38±0.22	19.42±0.28*	11.00±0.00	17.45±0.26*
40	17.30±0.20*	15.65±0.22	11.00±0.00	15.52±0.23*
30	14.52±0.18*	15.60±0.20*	11.00±0.00	11.82±0.12
20	11.88±0.12	13.57±0.18*	11.00±0.00	11.73±0.11
10	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00	11.00±0.00
Positive control	22.00±0.00	21.00±0.00	18.00±0.00	20.00±0.00
Negative control	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00

* Statistically significant difference ($p < 0.05$) observed among inhibition zones of tested oil concentrations against the same microorganism.

As shown in Table 4, peppermint essential oil demonstrated a moderate effect against *E. coli* at 100% (25.50 ± 0.63 mm), but the inhibition decreased substantially at lower concentrations. For *S. aureus*, the inhibition zone was 24.33 ± 0.43 mm at 100%, decreasing to 11.00 ± 0.00 mm at 10%, indicating weak activity. Against *P. aeruginosa*, peppermint oil exhibited almost no antimicrobial activity, except at the highest concentrations (100%, 90%, 80%), where zones remained below the threshold for meaningful inhibition. For *C. albicans*, a moderate effect was present at 100% (23.67 ± 0.42 mm), but it rapidly decreased at lower concentrations. According to the defined criteria, peppermint essential oil displayed moderate activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *C. albicans*, and was ineffective against *P. aeruginosa*.

Discussion

The results from the current study confirm the significant potential of essential oils as natural antimicrobial agents against foodborne pathogens, albeit with varying degrees of efficacy across different oils and microbial species.

These findings are consistent with previously published data that highlight the broad-spectrum activity of phenolic-rich essential oils, particularly those containing cinnamaldehyde, thymol, and carvacrol (Dorman & Deans, 2000; Raut & Karuppaiyil, 2014; Atki *et al.*, 2019).

Thyme essential oil exhibited particularly strong inhibition against *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*, which aligns with existing literature emphasizing the potent antifungal and antibacterial activity of thymol- and carvacrol-rich oils (Popova & Bankova, 2016; Mihaylova *et al.*, 2025).

The pronounced effect observed against *C. albicans* in our study supports results reported by Pinto *et al.* (2006), who also documented low MIC values of thyme-derived components against various *Candida* species.

Our findings further confirm the strong effect of thyme essential oil against *C. albicans* and *S. aureus*, which is attributed to its high content of thymol and carvacrol (Lopez *et al.*, 2022). Reported inconsistencies regarding its activity against *P. aeruginosa* (Millezi *et al.*, 2012; Al-Bayati, 2008) are reflected in our results, which showed only minimal inhibition. Black pepper essential oil displayed selective and limited antimicrobial activity, primarily against *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, while showing no effect on *P. aeruginosa* or *C. albicans*. The inhibition observed against *E. coli* supports findings by Zhang *et al.* (2017). The negligible inhibition against *P. aeruginosa* is also supported by Alves *et al.* (2023), who noted the inactivity of black pepper extracts and its isolated alkaloid piperine against this specific Gram-negative pathogen.

These results align with other studies confirming that piperine – the main active component of black pepper – exhibits weak activity against Gram-negative bacteria and yeasts.

Cinnamon essential oil emerged as the most effective agent, demonstrating powerful inhibitory effects across all tested microorganisms. This superior efficacy is attributed to cinnamaldehyde, which disrupts bacterial membranes (Atki *et al.*, 2019). Our observed high antifungal effect against *C. albicans* is consistent with the findings of Raut *et al.* (2014) and Hurtado *et al.* (2020).

Its effect against *P. aeruginosa* is particularly notable, as many studies report inconsistent inhibition due to the pathogen's intrinsic resistance mechanisms (Burt, 2004). However, our results agree with Van *et al.* (2022), who demonstrated that certain essential oils can inhibit antibiotic-resistant strains.

Peppermint essential oil showed the weakest overall effect, primarily exhibiting moderate inhibition against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, and *C. albicans*, and being largely ineffective against *P. aeruginosa*.

This agrees with studies attributing peppermint's lower efficacy to its menthol-rich composition (Mahboubi & Kazempour, 2014; Gómez-Sequeda *et al.*, 2020).

The results obtained in this study are consistent with several Bulgarian investigations on the antimicrobial activity of essential oils.

Mihaylova *et al.* (2025) demonstrated the strong inhibitory effect of thyme and oregano oils against multidrug-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *P. aeruginosa*, supporting our observation that thyme oil possesses significant antimicrobial potential.

Tsankova *et al.* (2025) reported that combining *Thymus vulgaris* essential oil with conventional antibiotics enhances antibacterial activity, which suggests possible synergy between natural and synthetic antimicrobials – a concept relevant to our findings for resistant organisms such as *P. aeruginosa*.

Popova & Bankova (2016) and Parzhanova *et al.* (2023) further documented strong antimicrobial effects of essential oils from Bulgarian plant species, reinforcing the relevance of essential oils as natural bioactive agents with potential applications in food safety and veterinary practice.

The varying efficacy of the essential oils observed in this study can be attributed to differences in their chemical composition.

Cinnamon and thyme oils, rich in phenolic and aldehyde compounds, demonstrated membrane-disrupting properties, while peppermint and black pepper oils, containing primarily monoterpenes or alkaloids, showed comparatively weaker effects. This pattern has been consistently reported in multiple studies (Dorman & Deans, 2000; Burt, 2004; Nazzaro *et al.*, 2013).

Across all tested microorganisms, *P. aeruginosa* was the most resistant, which is consistent with its well-established resistance mechanisms (Burt, 2004).

Despite this, cinnamon oil demonstrated measurable inhibition, suggesting its potential as part of future strategies targeting difficult-to-treat Gram-negative pathogens.

The inhibitory effect of cinnamon oil on *P. aeruginosa* is particularly relevant given the global concern surrounding antimicrobial resistance and the search for alternative or complementary antimicrobial strategies.

Microbial Resistance and Overall Efficacy

The overall evaluation confirms the superior performance of cinnamon essential oil, followed by thyme, while peppermint and black pepper demonstrated limited activity. Consistently, *P. aeruginosa* was the most resistant strain across all essential oils tested. This high resistance is a known characteristic of the species due to intrinsic mechanisms like efflux pumps, reduced cell wall permeability, and the ability to rapidly form biofilms (Burt, 2004). These factors impede the accessibility and efficacy of many antimicrobial agents, including essential oils. Despite this general resistance, some studies, such as Van *et al.* (2022), have shown that essential oils like thyme can still be effective against antibiotic-resistant *P. aeruginosa* strains, particularly by inhibiting biofilm formation at sub-inhibitory concentrations, pointing to potential future applications in mitigating antimicrobial resistance.

Conclusion

This study confirms the significant antimicrobial potential of the tested essential oils as natural alternatives to control foodborne pathogens. Efficacy was found to be specific to the microbial species. Cinnamon essential oil and thyme essential oil exhibited the strongest overall activity, showing high inhibition against the key pathogens *E. coli* and *S. aureus*. Conversely, *P. aeruginosa* and *C. albicans* showed greater resistance to most essential oils.

These findings strongly support the use of essential oils, particularly cinnamon and thyme, as natural preservatives in the food industry and in the development of novel antimicrobial agents to address antimicrobial resistance.

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